

SRI LANKAS ECONOMIC CRISIS: REVIEW BAD TO WORSE

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Abstract:

Sri Lanka is currently experiencing a socioeconomic and political crisis and successive failure of government on many fronts leads to this financial crisis but actual indicators for the failure have already been shown in many ways in Sri Lanka. As the inflation rate reached up to 18 per cent this could be an alarm signal for the government to act so it will relieve the common man. Sri Lanka defaults \$51 billion in external debt. There is no food available and commodity prices are very high so it could not possible to purchase. Sri Lanka has fallen into poverty. There is no fuel, no medicines, and critical surgeries are being cancelled. According to doctors, the economic crisis may cause more deaths in Sri Lanka than COVID did. There is a number of protection on street. The people of Sri Lanka struggling to get basic amenities. The absence of power resulted in many problems and religious fights among the citizens. Many emergency services have been suspended due to power failure. Items like milk, medical, emergency services and others have been affected.

Plan and policy have been drastically changed. The situation in Sri Lanka is much more than just an economic crisis. Now, this is a humanitarian crisis. Sri Lanka still has a long way to go to come out of this crisis, which has been a long time in the making. Decades of fiscal deficits, current account deficits, a bloated public sector, diminishing tax revenue, and subsidized prices have led to this state. Currently, the country is looking at an IMF bailout, for which it needs to restructure its debt. Debt restructuring can be complicated, especially in China, which prefers to refinance loans instead of restructuring approaches. With this paper, researchers want to understand the basic aspect behind the crisis. Understand the loopholes that make a failure of the Sri Lankan economy, and how the allocation of money has been done by the government. How does it happen? The purpose of the research paper is to answer the basic question of this financial crisis.

Key Words: Financial Crisis, Emergency Services, Bailout, Fiscal Deficits.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the Presidential Palace has been one of Sri Lanka's grandest and most heavily guarded buildings, serving as the residence of the President of Sri Lanka. But that all changed in July 2022 when protesters flooded in to take control and demand the president's resignation before toppling the palace. "This was the home of the most powerful man in Sri Lanka.' It was never open to the public because it was very heavily guarded'. (<https://edition.cnn.com>, srilankas crisis, 2022)

(Report, 2011) Sri Lankan government troops were responsible for abuses common people by way of atrocity on their civilian. A number of credible sources have estimated there could have been as many as 40,000 civilian deaths reported during decades." (Satkunanathan, 2022) Sri Lanka's next long-term leader must "tackle entrenched problems like ethnic conflict, disparity, accountability for human rights violations, as well as possess the commitment and integrity to rebuild public trust." "Because we simply can't afford to slip back yet again into a crisis like the one we face today in Srilanka."

"The urgent priority is a peaceful transition of power that respects rights and addresses the root causes of the political and economic crises, ultimately ending with a lack of accountability, corruption, and control of power. "If a more stable government is not formed in the allotted time, there is a risk of humanitarian crises and an increased likelihood of violence and repression, attacks, and emergencies. (<https://edition.cnn.com>, sri lanka crisis, 2022)

The crisis has long been in the making; successive governments have failed to enact policies that insert Sri Lanka into the global supply chain, instead opting for protectionist measures. This has exacerbated the “twin deficit” problem in which Sri Lanka faces both a budget deficit and a current account deficit (<https://edition.cnn.com>, srilankas crisis, 2022).

(IMF, 2020) Sri Lanka’s debt obligations have expanded as politicians invest in infrastructure projects, including a number of commercially enviable vanity projects. Sri Lanka has risen this funding from both international investors, who account for about 37 percent of the country’s overall debt profile, and bilateral creditors such as China and Japan. (IMF, 2020) China is Sri Lanka’s largest bilateral creditor, accounting for about 10.8 percent of Sri Lanka’s overall debt. These debt obligations are a major reason why Sri Lanka is facing this current crisis. Implemented a value-added tax cut and an income tax cut despite warnings from the International Monetary Fund, for unknown reason government waived taxes GST.

(IMF, 2020) These tax cuts have cost Sri Lanka lost more than 2% of its gross domestic product, impacting its ability to service its debt. Another premature policy was to implement a ban on the import of non-organic fertilizers without preparing farmers for the change. Rice production fell by about 20% in half a year; forcing the government to import about \$450 million worth of rice, further putting pressure on foreign exchange reserves. Combined with her COVID-19 pandemic, which has led to a significant drop in tourism, and Russia's invasion of Ukraine, which has boosted the price of oil and commodities, these two measures will allow Sri Lanka to move into her May 2022 We were forced to default on gasoline and blackouts. For up to 13 hours a day, ordinary Sri Lankan citizens have taken to the streets to demand the government's resignation as it has not addressed the situation. (<https://www.cfr.org/blog>, 2022)

The government mainly blamed the Covid-19 pandemic, which badly affected Sri Lanka's tourist trade - one of its biggest foreign currency earners. However, many experts blame poor economic mismanagement is also one of cause. Sri Lanka chose to focus on providing goods to its domestic market, instead of trying to boost foreign trade. This meant its income from exports to other countries remained low, while the bill for imports kept growing and it had affected profit of government. (<https://www.moneycontrol.com/news>, 2022)

Sri Lanka currently imports \$3 billion (£2.3 billion) more than it exports each year, resulting in a foreign exchange shortage. At the end of 2019, Sri Lanka's foreign exchange reserves were at her \$7.6bn (£5.8bn), but had fallen to around \$250m (£210m). The president has also been criticized for the drastic tax cuts he introduced in 2019, which have taken the government to over \$1.4 billion (£1.13 billion) in annual revenue. (treasury.gov.lk, 2022) The Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 made the bad situation worse Exports of tea, rubber, spices and garments suffered. Tourism arrivals and revenues fell further Due to a rise in government expenditures, the fiscal deficit exceeded 10% in 2020-21, and the debt to GDP ratio rose from 94% in 2019 to 119% in 2021. (treasury.gov.lk, 2022)

The Crisis in Sri Lanka is triggered due to a shortage of foreign exchange (forex) reserves, which have dropped by 70% over the last two years to just USD 2 billion by the end of February 2022. Meanwhile, the country has foreign debt obligations of about USD 7 billion for 2022. (ADO, 2022)

Sri Lanka is scheduled to participate in many international tournaments at Asian and World level but many sports bodies are unable to submit their entries because of the dollar crisis. (<https://www.dailymirror.lk/sports>, 2022)

2. METHODOLOGY

Many articles from 2020 to today are filtered. Duplicates and unreliable sources were removed and only 45 popular messages were included in the study. However, the keywords 'Sri Lanka Economy' and 'Lanka' and 'Economic and Political Crisis Sri Lanka' have only had negative news due to the lack of balance of payments reports for the past two years. This is also a notable observation when searching for information about web content.

3. SRI LANKA GDP

Source: (<https://www.adb.org/news>, 2022)

According to the (SLTDA, 2021) **Sri Lanka Tourism Development Authority (SLTDA)**, the number of tourist arrivals decreased by 60 per cent in June. The situation had arisen due to the unprecedented economic crisis. As per SLTDA data, 106,500 tourists arrived in March 2022, but the number dwindled to 32,856 in June. July and August are the best months for tourism in Sri Lanka. Tourism earned Sri Lanka USD 4.4 billion and contributed 5.6 per cent to GDP in 2018, but this dropped to just 0.8 per cent in 2020 due to many reasons.

Source: (<https://www.adb.org/news>, 2022)

(IMF, 2020) The government was left with a large deficit. Sri Lanka fell back on its foreign exchange reserves to pay off government debt, shrinking its reserves from USD 6.9 billion in 2018 to USD 2.2 billion this year. This year, Sri Lankans facing with long power cuts, shortages of fuel and gas and soaring prices of food. The country, with an acute foreign currency crisis that resulted in foreign debt default, had announced in April that it is suspending nearly \$7 billion foreign debt repayment due for this year out of about \$25 billion due through 2026. Sri Lanka's total foreign debt stands at \$51 billion. (<https://www.theweek.in/news>, 2021)

The textile hub of Tamil Nadu and tea estates of southern India and Assam are witnessing a surge in overseas orders as the export demand has diverted to India from Sri Lanka owing to the economic and political crisis in the island nation. Garments and tea are the major exporters from Sri Lanka (<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com>, 2022). The UK is Sri Lanka's third biggest source of inbound tourists behind Russia and India. Tourism accounts for about 5 per cent of Sri Lanka's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), with Britain, India and China being the main markets. (<https://www.hindustantimes.com>, 2021)

Sources (World Bank,2022)

4. INFLATION IS RECORD HIGH IN SRILANKA

Source (https://www.dailymirror.lk, 2022)

Prices Rising:

The retail price of rice in the last week was 60 per cent more than the year-ago level, while the price of onions was 78 per cent, that of potatoes 65 per cent, and that of an egg was 94 per cent higher year-on-year.

Source: (CBS, 2021)

Prices shot up as much as 200%
Cost of essentials on March 23, 2022 and March 23, 2021, in Sri Lankan Rs

	2022	2021
Tomato	320	120
Dal	420	180
Coconut	110	50
Egg	30.5	15
Coconut oil	852	486
Potato (local)	280	160
Brinjal	240	140
Sugar	188	112
Carrot	240	160
Rice	185	128
Big onion (imported)	170	120

*The price for coconut oil is for a litre and for eggs that of one piece. For all others, costs are for a kg
Source: Central Bank of Sri Lanka

Source: (CBS, 2021)

Altogether, headline inflation rose to 18.7 per cent in March 2022 from 15.1 per cent in February 2022. Food inflation stood at 30.2 per cent in March,

(CBS, 2021) "The import price of crude oil significantly increased by 45.9 per cent in January 2022 (Y-o-Y). Further, the import prices of sugar and wheat increased by 21.1 per cent and 18.6 per cent respectively, in January 2022 (Y-o-Y)," the country's central bank explained. (<https://www.indiatoday.in>, 2021)

Source: (<https://www.aljazeera.com>, 2021)

The island nation’s foreign reserves stood at a paltry \$1.93bn at the end of March, with foreign debt payments of about \$4bn due this year, including a \$1bn international sovereign bond maturing in July. Despite citizen protests against inflation that’s running at 17-20 32 percent and daily electricity cuts of as long as 13 hours. (<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com>, 2021)

(CBS, 2021) Sri Lanka’s gross debt servicing would amount to \$7bn in 2022 and a current account deficit of approximately \$3bn. “The market was expecting this default to come and now we have to see how the new government handles the onshore chaos.”

Sri Lankan doctors warn life-saving drugs are running out, and say the country's economic crisis threatens a higher death toll than the coronavirus pandemic. Power outages and severe shortages of food, fuel and medicine have left Sri Lanka in a state of widespread devastation, suffering its worst recession since independence in 1948. (<https://www.theguardian.com>, 2022).

Source: (New18, 2022)

5. AGRICULTURE CRISIS

In 2021, suddenly all fertilizer imports were completely banned and Sri Lanka was declared to become a 100% organic farming country overnight. This overnight switch to organic fertilizers had a significant impact on food production. As a result, Sri Lanka's president declared an economic emergency to stem rising food prices, currency depreciation and a rapid depletion of foreign exchange reserves. (<https://www.drishtias.com>, 2021)

The rice and banana farmer no longer has the income to run his farm after a government ban on chemical fertilizers cut his rice yield in half during the March harvest season. Especially since his banana harvest is doomed to failure. His two million farmers, who make up 30% of his workforce and had hitherto relied on subsidized chemical fertilizers, were suddenly forced to fend for themselves. They said the government has not increased organic fertilizer production or imported enough soil nutrients to meet their needs.. (<https://www.drishtias.com>, 2021)

(WorldBank, 2021) has given us money to buy fertiliser and a few other agencies and countries are to help us too” But with Sri Lanka’s foreign reserves having dwindled to \$1.8bn at the end of April and Russia’s invasion of Ukraine pushing up fertiliser prices in the world market, experts said it is not clear how the government can afford to import enough soil nutrients for its two million farmers, much less subsidies them.

(Weerakoon, 2022) The government and private parties had spent about \$259m on importing fertiliser in 2020. The bill for 2021 could be between \$300m-440m and potentially double that this year.

The government has kept its promises, banning the import and use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides nationwide and ordering the country's two million farmers to switch to organic farming. Domestic rice production, a conventional farm, fell by 20% in his first six months alone. Long self-sufficient in rice, Sri Lanka has been forced to import \$450 million worth of rice, even as domestic prices for the nation's staple food have risen by about 50%. It has been. The ban also hit the country's tea production, a major export and source of foreign currency. The government has also provided the farmer with her direct compensation of US\$200 million and a further US\$149 million in subsidies to the rice farmers who suffered losses. It has barely made up for the damage and suffering caused by the ban. Farmers are very poorly paid and provide one of the main sources of employment for many farmers, especially in rural Sri Lanka. It has been widely criticized for shutting out tea producers who

do The reduction in tea production alone is estimated to result in an economic loss of US\$425 million.(<https://foreignpolicy.com>, 2021)

6. CHINA ROLES AND DEBT TRAP ON SRI LANKA

Sri Lanka has borrowed heavily from Beijing for infrastructure projects since 2005, much of which has become a white elephant (no longer necessary/useful). Sri Lanka also leased Hambantota port to a Chinese company in 2017 after failing to repay a \$1.4 billion debt from Beijing used to build Hambantota port. Sri Lanka's \$81 billion economy is on the brink of collapse. The country now has to pay back more than three times her foreign exchange reserves, putting it at risk of default. There are many contributing factors to the ongoing crisis, from debt traps to inflation. Sri Lanka has about US\$2 billion in foreign exchange reserves and her total debt service target for 2022 is US\$7 billion. Of these, US\$1 billion worth of bonds will mature in July 2022. Sri Lanka's external debt has increased sharply since 2005. In 2005 he was US\$11.3 billion, in 2010 he was US\$21.7 billion, in 2015 he was US\$43.9 billion, and in 2020 he was US\$56.3 billion during the Covid pandemic. Did. China accounted for her 10% of loans, and in April 2021 India accounted for her 2%.

Source:(Resources, 2022)

The trouble was that the country’s external debt rose quicker than the GDP. The external debt to GDP ratio rose from 31.6 per cent in 2010 to 32.4 per cent in 2015, and further to 40.4 per cent in 2020.

(Source: Department of External Resource, Sri Lanka)

(Resources, 2022) Despite the country's attempts to rebuild its economy amid the pandemic, tourism has been hit hard, with Sri Lanka's tourism supporting 10-15% of the economy. The impact of the COVID-19 crisis, the loss of tourists, the reduction in government revenues due to high government spending and tax cuts, and the use of funds for minimally profitable initiatives have all contributed to Sri Lanka's economic collapse. I'm here. The 9th, 10th, and 11th grade semester tests are part of an ongoing evaluation process that determines whether students will advance to the next grade at the end of the school year. An economic crisis caused by a shortage of foreign exchange reserves to fund essential imports has left the country running out of food, fuel and medicine. (<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2022>, 2022)

Russia is the third largest market for Sri Lanka's tea exports. The war between Russia and Ukraine has resulted in Russia being blocked from her global SWIFT payment system, leaving the country unable to pay Sri Lanka. Sri Lanka asked China for help, asking for her \$1 billion loan to repay and her \$1.5 billion line of credit to purchase Chinese goods, but even after months of negotiations, no progress seen. (<https://theprint.in>, 2022) Sri Lanka couldn't tap a \$1.5 billion credit line from China and has yet to hear back on the request to China for a \$1 billion loan, (Bloomberg, 2022) "China is, of course, a very important creditor of Sri Lanka. Sri Lanka is clearly unable to repay that debt. And it's my hope that China will be willing to work with Sri Lanka to restructure the debt — it would likely be both in China and Sri Lanka's interest," (Yellen, 2022). Political observers underline Sri Lanka is currently in a tough spot over debt owed to China.

7. GOVERNMENT MEASURES

Short-term import restrictions may have reduced spending and thus the trade balance, but since Sri Lanka's export industry relies heavily on imports of intermediate capital goods, a long-term import ban would also affect exports. The import ban has had a negative impact on many importers. The government's policy of banning chemical fertilizers has also been heavily criticized as it could affect agricultural production and escalate food insecurity in the country.

(EU, 2022) The European Union and the embassies of France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands and Romania issued a joint statement on November 19, 2020, criticizing the Sri Lankan government's import restrictions, arguing that the extension of the import ban is inconsistent with global trade. Organizational regulations and this can have a negative impact on foreign direct investment as well as Sri Lankan and European companies. Indian aid is also helping to address fuel shortages. Sri Lanka relies heavily on her US\$1 billion from India to pay for imports of food and medicines. (Minister, 2020)

(Fernando, 2022) Bangladesh has extended a \$200 million currency swap facility. China expands \$1.5 billion swap facility Sri Lanka has also received her US\$700 million from the China Development Bank. India has so far pledged US\$2.4 billion in financial support for her, including: (a) US\$400 million under the SAARC Currency Swap Agreement; (b) A.C.U. deferred two-month comparison of \$515.2 million. (c) her US\$500 million for importing fuel from India; (d) her US\$1 billion in importing food, essentials and medicines; In addition, Indian Oil Corporation delivered her 40,000 tons of fuel on her 60-day credit. (<https://www.ndtv.com>, 2022). As part of the financial assistance package, India also agreed to actively contribute to improving Sri Lanka's energy security by signing a memorandum of understanding to jointly develop the Trincomalee Oil Terminal. Pakistan and Qatar also agreed to aid. Pakistan has agreed to provide her \$200 million credit line for the importation of cement, basmati rice and pharmaceuticals manufactured in Pakistan. Details have yet to be finalized between the two countries. CBSL has reportedly entered into talks with the Qatar Central Bank to secure a swap worth over \$1 billion. (CBS, 2021)

(IMF, 2020) Sri Lanka needs at least USD 4 billion to tide over its mounting economic woes, and authority has been holding talks with the World Bank and countries like China and Japan for Financial assistance. Going forward, the IMF team will support Sri Lanka's efforts to overcome the current economic crisis by working closely with the

authorities on their economic programme, and by engaging with all other stakeholders in support of a timely resolution of the crisis, (<https://www.business-standard.com>, 2022)

(CBS, 2021) Central bank data obtained by Reuters, Sri Lanka currently has about \$2 billion in foreign exchange reserves against \$7 billion in total debt due this year, including \$1 billion worth of notes maturing in July. (<https://www.cnbc.com>, 2022)

(WorldBank, 2021) Sri Lanka will receive \$300 million to \$600 million from the World Bank over the next four months to buy medicine and other essential items, the country's finance minister authority, as the Indian ocean island suffers its worst economic crisis in decades. Neighboring India has also agreed to provide \$500 million to purchase fuel, and negotiations are underway on an additional \$1 billion from New Delhi, which has already provided a credit line of \$ 1 billion. (<https://economictimes.com>, 2022)

8. CHALLENGES FOR INDIA

Sri Lanka's share of India's total exports fell from 2.16% in FY2015 to just 1.3% in FY2022. Auto companies such as Tata Motors and TVS Motors have stopped exporting vehicle kits to Sri Lanka and halted production at assembly plants in Sri Lanka due to unstable foreign exchange reserves and fuel shortages. Whenever there is a political or social crisis in Sri Lanka, India has seen a massive influx of refugees from the Tamil community into India from the Sinhala country through the Palk Strait and Munnar Bay.

Sri Lanka's economy is declining rapidly. However, the contagion from the Lanka crisis has also hit Indian companies such as the auto sector. ITC's first foreign-affiliated company in the hotel sector was hit hard. Earlier, construction of his \$300 million project in Colombo was affected by the 2019 terrorist attacks and subsequent pandemic. (financialDaily, 2022) Automotive firms like Tata Motors, Mahindra & Mahindra, Ashok Leyland, and TVS Motors had stopped exports of vehicle kits to Sri Lanka and halted production at their Sri Lankan assembly units due to its precarious forex reserves and fuel shortages. Instability in Sri Lanka could affect Indian Oil, Airtel, Taj Hotels, Dabur, Ashok Leyland, Tata Communications, Asian Paints, and State Bank of India.

Meanwhile, Sri Lanka's share in India's total exports has declined from 2.16 per cent in FY15 to just 1.3 per cent in the first 10 months of FY22. India's export to Sri Lanka is now nowhere near the 6.7 billion dollars seen in 2014-15. Till January 2022, it stood at 4.49 billion dollars in FY22. (www.business-standard.com, 2022) principal cause of the problem—linking the fall in earnings from the tourism sector (one of the most significant

contributors to Sri Lanka's GDP) from over US\$4 billion in 2018 to less than the US \$150 million in 2021 to the drop in the country's forex reserves—this crisis long been in the making. Between 2009 and 2018, Sri Lanka's trade deficit swelled from US\$5 billion to US\$12 billion.

9. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

1. Improving agricultural productivity in all areas of agriculture is the first important aspect. The use of organic farming with chemicals and fertilizers should be approved with immediate effect by governments. All farmers in the country are required to use organic fertilizers and the country aims to replace all synthetic fertilizers in the next decade or time. For a country that relies as heavily on its agricultural industry as its pandemic-hit tourism sector, this will help boost the productivity of rice, coconuts and other crops in Sri Lanka's agriculture.
2. Investment in non-agricultural job creation. In a country as dependent on tourism as Sri Lanka, where the sector is his third largest market in the country, the Covid-19 pandemic has dealt a fatal blow to economic growth. Declining international tourism means less funding for projects to develop new hospitality infrastructure. But a World Bank report urges governments to invest foreign aid in tourism development and expansion.
3. Welfare scheme is what the country needs to develop and put in place. Owing to the unregulated hours and low pay in the informal labour market, productivity is abysmal.
4. Government education, worker health and general benefits will go a long way as productivity increases. Additionally, Sri Lanka needs to establish more government-funded educational institutions to enable more Sri Lankans to use their skills for better industrialization of the agriculture and tourism sectors.
5. The crisis has severe implications for human rights, Sri Lankan experts said. Continuing disruptions in access to food and health care are severely impacting the sick, pregnant women, nursing mothers and the elderly in dire need of life support.
6. Sri Lanka needs extensive economic reforms to achieve long-term sustainable growth in order to be able to repay its debt. We also need stable governments to emerge stronger from this crisis. Stable monetary policy is critical to maintaining macroeconomic stability and confidence in local currencies. The current economic crisis facing Sri Lanka makes it clear that an independent central bank is paramount.
7. Fair taxation system should be imposing as per requirement of government and can

adopt changes as per need from the market.

8. The country's prolonged political instability in the country may delay progress on negotiations with the International Monetary Fund for a bailout package.

Conclusion:

The economy has endured several shocks in recent years with a number of policy actions. A 'catastrophic' collapse of organic farming with massive tax cuts, interest rate cuts and a ban on the import of all fertilizers and pesticides. adopted by the government; most recently, it also had to deal with an unexpected increase in import bills due to the Ukrainian crisis. The country's current external debt stands at over \$50 billion, most of which (nearly 47%) is borrowed from the market, primarily through international government bonds (ISBs). for 2-month imports). Slow and steadily government should advocate all essential measure for the upliftment of all section from the society especially poor from the crisis.

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